

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by hexamethylenetetramine-bromine

Meenakshi Aneja, Pradeep K. Sharma and Kalyan K. Banerji*

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, India

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Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR) have been studied in acetic acid-water (1 : 1). The main product of oxidation is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to HABR. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics have been observed with respect to the reductants. The oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid (DFA) exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 6.11$ at 303 K). Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR) has been reported as a mild and selective synthetic reagent for the oxidation of alcohol to carbonyl compounds and for the regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes and hydrazones^{1,2}. However, there seems to be a few reports on the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation reactions of HABR available in the literature³⁻⁶. The kinetics of oxidation of organic acids by HABR have not been reported. Here, we report the kinetics of the oxidation of oxalic acid (OA) and formic acid (FA) by HABR in acetic acid.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are of first order with respect to HABR. The reaction rate increases with an increase in [organic acid] but not linearly (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{organic acid}]$ is linear ($r > 0.990$) with an intercept on

postulation of following overall mechanism (eqns. 1 and 2) and the rate law (3),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{HABR}] [\text{Organic acid}] / (1 + K [\text{Organic acid}]) \quad (3)$$

The dependence of k_{obs} on the [organic acid] was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double-reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively, at different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of organic acids by HABR at 303 K

$10^3 [\text{HABR}]$ mol dm ⁻³	[Acid] mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
		Oxalic acid	Formic acid
1.0	0.02	41.8	1.56
1.0	0.04	63.3	3.00
1.0	0.06	76.5	5.49
1.0	0.12	96.6	12.4
1.0	0.24	111	18.1
1.0	0.40	118	22.2
1.0	0.80	124	26.8
1.0	1.00	126	28.0
2.0	0.02	42.5	1.66
4.0	0.02	41.0	1.41
6.0	0.02	41.5	1.50
8.0	0.02	42.0	1.60
1.0	0.04	41.0 ^a	1.63 ^a
1.0	0.04	42.2 ^b	1.45 ^b

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile. ^bContained 0.005 mol dm⁻³ HXA.

Table 2. Formation constant and thermodynamic parameters for the organic acid-HABR complexes

Acid	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
	303	308	313	318 K			
OA	23.4	10.6	5.05	2.31	-126 ± 1	-380 ± 4	-12.4 ± 0.9
FA	4.88	3.66	2.71	2.11	-47.6 ± 0.6	-136 ± 2	-7.17 ± 0.5
DFA	5.22	4.05	3.18	2.55	-40.8 ± 0.4	-113 ± 1	-7.21 ± 3

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters for the decomposition of HABR-organic acid complexes

Acid	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
	303	308	313	318 K			
OA	13.1	18.5	26.9	38.8	55.6 ± 0.9	-79 ± 3	79.1 ± 0.7
FA	3.36	4.83	6.91	9.96	55.5 ± 0.5	-91 ± 2	82.4 ± 0.4
DFA	0.55	0.82	1.23	1.81	61.2 ± 0.4	-87 ± 1	86.9 ± 0.3
k_H/k_D	6.11	5.89	5.62	5.50			

The oxidation of organic acids by HABR, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no

the rate ordinate. Thus, Michaelis-Menten type kinetics are observed with respect to the organic acids. This leads to the

effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid (DFA) was studied. It was observed that the formation constants of the complexes of ordinary and deuteriated formic acids had similar values but the rate of decomposition of the complexes showed a considerable primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.82$ at 308 K). This confirms the cleavage of the C-H bond in the rate-determining step of the oxidation of formic acid. The rate of oxidation of organic acid is not affected by the addition hexamethylenetetramine (HXA) (Table 1).

In solution, HABR may dissociate to form molecular bromine,

The probable oxidizing species in a solution of HABR are, therefore, HABR itself, molecular bromine and its acetolysis product. An addition of HXA should result in the suppression of decomposition of HABR and should result in a decrease in the reaction rate if bromine is the reactive oxidizing species. Therefore, the no effect of HXA and strict first order dependence on HABR rule out both bromine and its acetolysis product as the reactive oxidizing species. Thus the most likely reactive oxidizing species is HABR itself.

A perusal of UV-VIS spectra of HABR (0.001 mol dm⁻³) and an equivalent amount of bromine (0.002 mol dm⁻³), in acetic acid at ≈ 293 K, shows that the difference in the nature of the spectra of HABR and bromine is not very striking but their optical densities show variations (Fig. 1). HXA had no appreciable absorption in this range. Further, the spectrum of HABR does not show any change in the experimental time period (*ca.* 2 h). When a solution of HABR in acetic acid was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, HABR was recovered unchanged. This confirmed that HABR retained its integrity in acetic acid. This supports the postulation of HABR as the reactive oxidizing species.

Fig. 1.

The rate of oxidation was determined in solvents of different amounts of acetic acid and water. It was observed

that the rate of reaction increases with an increase in the amount of water in the solvent mixture (Table 4). This showed that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. The plot of $\log k_{obs}$ against the inverse of the dielectric constant is nonlinear. The solvent effect was analysed using Winstein-Grunwald equation⁷, $\log k = \log k_0 + mY$. The plot of $\log k_{obs}$ versus Y is linear ($r = 0.9982$) with $m = 0.44 \pm 0.01$. The value of m points to a transition state which is more polar than the reactants. Thus considerable charge separation takes place in the transition state of the reaction.

Table 4. Effect of solvent composition in the oxidation of organic acids by HABR

[HABR] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [Organic acid] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K

	% AcOH				
% AcOH	40	50	60	72	
$10^3 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)					
Oxalic acid	310	205	126	79.4	49.7
Formic acid	69.7	44.6	28.0	18.1	11.2

Mechanism : The observed Michaelis-Menten kinetics with respect to the organic acid lead us to suggest that an intermediate complex may be formed by the interaction between the non-bonded pairs of electrons of carboxylic oxygen and HABR in a rapid pre-equilibrium (Scheme 1). The formation of similar complexes has also been postulated in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes⁴ and diols⁵ with HABR as well as in the oxidation of alcohols and organic acids with pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide⁸. The entropy of the complex formation, in the oxidation of oxalic acid, is much more negative (*ca.* 3 times) than in the oxidation of formic acid. Thus the HABR-OA complex is more rigid than the HABR-FA complex. Hence, it is likely that, in the case of oxalic acid, both the carboxylic acid groups are involved in the complex formation. The experimental results can be accounted for a proposed mechanism in terms of formation of cyclic/acyclic intermediate complexes in the pre-equilibrium and their subsequent decomposition in the rate-determining step.

Scheme 1

The above mechanism is supported by the observed negative entropy of activation also. As the charge separation takes place, in the transition state of the rate-determining step, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy. The low magnitude of the ΔH^* and the large magnitude ΔS^* indicate that the reaction is entropy-controlled. The low value of ΔH^* also points out that in the rate-determining activated complex the bond-breaking and bond-formation are of almost equal magnitude.

Experimental

HABR and α -deuterioformic acid (DCOOH or DFA) were prepared by the reported methods^{1,9}. Acetic acid was purified by refluxing it with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then fractionally distilled¹⁰.

To determine the stoichiometry, an excess of HABR ($\times 5$ or greater) was reacted with the organic acid in acetic acid (100 ml) and the amount of residual HABR after the completion of reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at 394 nm. The results indicate 2 : 1 stoichiometry. No quantitative determination of carbon dioxide formed was carried out.

The oxidation of organic acids leads to the formation of carbon dioxide. The stoichiometric determination indicates the following overall reactions,

The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order con-

ditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the organic acid over HABR. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was acetic acid, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of HABR spectrophotometrically at 394 nm for upto 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}), were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.995-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{HABR}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$.

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